

Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Rauwolfia Serpentina*, Benth.

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Rauwolfia Serpentina, Benth, (Hindi, Chhota-chand, Sanskrit, Chandrika or Sarpagandha) is a short shrub inhabiting the moist and hot regions of India. Its roots, which are crooked, tapering and $\frac{1}{4}$ " to $\frac{1}{2}$ " in diameter in thickness, are mentioned in older literature as a febrifuge, a remedy for snake-bites and a cure for dysentery and other painful affections of the intestines. In comparatively later times the drug has gained the reputation of being a general sedative and a cure for certain types of insanity.

The chemical work so far done on the drug was limited to the detection of an alkaloidal principle in the roots by Dymock and coworkers (" Pharmacographia Indica, " Vol. II. p. 415), who also noted the presence of a yellow resin and a trace of a wax. As a result of our investigations we have obtained a total alkaloidal yield of 0.5 p.c. on the weight of the dry powdered root, and isolated out of it five crystalline alkaloids, which appear to be new from their general characteristics and could be classed into the following two the groups:—

A. The *Ajmaline group*, (so named by us in memory of the late Hakim Ajmal Khan, the founder of this Institute) consists of three white, crystalline, weaker bases:

(i) Ajmaline ($C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$), m.p. 158-60°; 0.1 p.c. on the wt. dry powdered root,

(ii) Ajmalinine ($C_{20}H_{23}O_4N$), m.p. 180-81°; 0.05 p.c. ,,

(iii) Ajmalicine — m.p. 250-52° (decomp.); 0.02 p.c. ,,

and an amorphous cream-coloured alkaloidal residue, forming about a quarter of the total alkaloidal yield, which is under further investigation.

B. The *Serpentine group*, consists of two bright yellow, crystalline stronger bases:

(i) Serpentine ($C_{21}H_{23}O_4N$), m.p. 153-54°; 0.08 p.c. on the wt. of dry powdered root.

(ii) Serpentinine ——— m.p. 263-65° (decomp.); ,,

and about 0.08 p.c. of a reddish-yellow uncrystallisable alkaloidal residue.

The method of separation of the alkaloids was chiefly based on the differences in the strength of the bases, on the one hand, and the solubilities of their hydrochlorides, on the other. Thus while the white group of the bases is completely precipitated from the aqueous solutions of its salts by dilute ammonia, a quantitative liberation of the serpentine group is possible only on addition of a strong solution of sodium hydroxide. Of the hydrochlorides of the bases, ajmaline hydrochloride is difficultly soluble in cold water and 10 p.c. aqueous or alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the hydrochlorides of ajmalinine and ajmalicine and the uncrystallised white alkaloid though varying in their solubilities in these solvents when pure, are together, easily soluble in them; and the hydrochlorides of the serpentine group are soluble in water and 10 p.c. alcoholic hydrochloric acid but insoluble in 10 p.c. aqueous hydrochloric acid.

The separation of ajmalinine and ajmalicine presented great difficulties and was possible only on a careful fractional precipitation of the bases by gradual addition of water to the alcoholic solution of the alkaloidal residue left after the isolation of ajmaline, ajmalinine being more soluble in a mixture of alcohol and water than ajmalicine but less soluble than the uncrystallised white base. Apart from the alkaloids we also isolated:

1. A *phytosterol*, $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$, melting at $159-60^\circ$, and showing $[\alpha]_D^{33} = -68.5^\circ$ in 1.3 p.c. chloroform solution, which we consider to be identical with mykosterin ($C_{30}H_{48}O_2$), m.p. $159-60^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D = -129.29^\circ$, -129.5° , but have, owing to the so far unaccountable difference in the optical rotatory power of the two compounds, provisionally called serposterin.

2. Oleic acid and a saturated acid melting at 58° , which is probably a mixture of stearic and palmitic acids.

3. A mixture of unsaturated alcohols corresponding to the formula $C_{25}H_{44}O_2$, which did not give any uniform product; and noted the presence of a resinous acid and a neutral resin which were not investigated further.

Pharmacological actions.—A series of preliminary experiments on frogs showed, that from the stand-point of physiological action also the white and the yellow bases form two distinct groups, the former acting as a general depressant of heart, respiration and nerves, and the latter as a paralysing agent of respiration and depressant of nerves, but a stimulant of the heart. The lethal dose of serpentine group of alkaloids

was found to be the same as that of the ajmaline group in case of frogs *viz.*, 0.5 g. per kg. weight of the body, but it was about four times higher for rats, being 0.05 g. per kg. body weight for serpentine and 1.2 g. per kg. body weight (12 g. for an adult human being) in case of ajmaline. In contrast to the lethal dose the minimum therapeutic dose of ajmaline, fixed on the basis of the dose of the crude drug and found effective by experience as a general sedative and hypnotic, is remarkably low, being only 0.005 to 0.01 g. for an adult. Clinical observations in respect of this as well as the other bases are in progress and the highly favourable results obtained in case of acute insomnia accompanied with fits of insanity promise it to form a valuable contribution to the list of existing sedatives.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The material used was obtained from the Patna markets by one of us personally and identified by the Sibpur Botanical Institute, Calcutta.

In illustration of the method worked out after a series of preliminary experiments for the separation of the different constituents, 5 kg. of well powdered drug were percolated six times with 90 p.c. alcohol, and the alcohol distilled off from the combined percolates under reduced pressure below 50°, till a thick greenish brown liquid was left behind. On complete removal of the solvent from an aliquot fraction of this liquid a semi-solid bitter extract was obtained, which was calculated out to form 10 p.c. of the weight of the dry roots. The total quantity of the crude extract was shaken out repeatedly with petroleum ether and then carefully concentrated further in *vacuo* till nearly all the solvent was removed. The light brown semi-solid extract was first treated with ammonia and then with caustic soda and extracted each time to exhaustion with ether containing a little alcohol. The alcoholic extract of the roots was thus subdivided into four fractions, the two middle, ethereal fractions constituting chiefly the alkaloidal contents (I), and the petroleum ether fraction and the final residue, the non alkaloidal contents (II).

I. The Alkaloidal Contents.

Separation of Ajmaline and Serpentine Groups.—The greenish ethereal solution obtained on treating the alcoholic extract with

ammonia and exhausting it with ether, was neutralised with acetic acid and freed of the solvent on the water-bath. The yellowish-brown paste, left behind as residue, was repeatedly digested with 5 per cent. acetic acid till all, except a little petroleum ether soluble residue, went into solution. The acetic acid solution was nearly neutralised with ammonia, the little dirty brown precipitate which was thereby produced was filtered off, and 15 per cent. hydrochloric acid added on to the filtrate under good cooling and shaking till no fresh precipitate formed on further addition of the acid. The hydrochloride precipitate (S) was filtered, washed with 10 per cent. warm hydrochloric acid and dried, and the reddish-yellow filtrate made alkaline with ammonia under good cooling. The copious cream coloured granular precipitate, which came down, was filtered, well washed and dried on a porous plate. The filtrate when shaken out with ether yielded a further small quantity of cream white bases from the ethereal layer (total yield 18 g.; 0.36 per cent. on the weight of the root).

The second ethereal fraction from the alcoholic extract containing the stronger bases was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas and the reddish-brown surupy precipitate of hydrochlorides, thereby obtained, was dissolved in hot water and filtered. The filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia and the small quantity of yellowish-white precipitate, which came down was worked up along with the first ethereal fraction of the alcoholic extract. The reddish-yellow filtrate from the precipitate gave a brilliant yellow flocculent precipitate, consisting chiefly of serpentine, on addition of a concentrated solution of caustic soda. The orange-coloured powder obtained on washing and drying the precipitate weighed 5 g. and along with the base from the hydrochloride precipitate (S), noted in the preceding paragraph, constituted the total yield, 9.5 g (0.2 per cent. of the serpentine group of alkaloids).

Isolation of the Alkaloids of the Ajmaline Group.

(i) *Ajmaline*.—The cream coloured amorphous powder constituting the total alkaloids of the white group (18 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of alcohol and ether (eventually also a little petroleum ether) added to the alcoholic solution to precipitate the impurities, which settled down as a dark brown paste. The light red filtrate was treated with ethereal hydrochloric acid till the bases were

completely precipitated as hydrochlorides. These were dissolved in the least quantity of a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 90 per cent. alcohol (1:3) and put in an ice-chest. The white crystalline powder of ajmaline hydrochloride which soon began to separate out, was filtered after a day, washed with a little alcohol and dried. It weighed 5.5 g. nearly (one third of the total yield of the ajmaline group) and after recrystallisation from the same medium melted at 133-34°. On addition of dilute ammonia to the aqueous solutions of the hydrochloride ajmaline was precipitated as snow white flocks, which when washed and dried formed a white amorphous powder melting at 158-60°. On slowly cooling a solution of the amorphous base in moist ethyl acetate, ajmaline crystallised out in large rectangular plates melting at 158-60° (yield 4.8 g.; about 0.1 per cent. on the weight of the root).

(ii) *Ajmalinine* and (iii) *Ajmalicine*.—The mother-liquor from ajmaline hydrochloride was diluted with water and made alkaline under ice-cooling with ammonia, which precipitated the remaining bases. These were washed and dried and once more purified by dissolving in alcohol and precipitating the impurities with ether and petroleum ether. The pale, straw coloured treacle left on removal of the solvents from the solution of the purified bases, was dissolved in absolute alcohol and the bases fractionally precipitated with water. After several repetitions of this process two fractions of nearly colourless, silky looking crystalline bases and a third fraction of an amorphous, cream coloured base were finally obtained. On crystallisation out of moist ethyl acetate, the first fraction yielded 1 g. of ajmalicine (0.02 per cent. on the weight of the roots) melting at 250-52° (decomp.) and the second fraction yielded ajmalinine (2.5 g., 0.05 per cent. of the roots), m.p. 180-81°. The third fraction weighed nearly 6.5 g. (0.13 per cent.) and could not be induced to yield any further crystalline base.

Isolation of the Alkaloids of the Serpentine Group.

(i) *Serpentine*.—The crude yellow alkaloids (9.5 g.) was dissolved in a little alcohol and ether added to the solution till no dark precipitate was formed on fresh addition of a little ether. The bright yellow ethereal solution of the purified bases was treated with hydrochloric acid gas and the reddish-yellow oily precipitate of hydrochloride, thus obtained, was dissolved in hot water and the bases

fractionally precipitated from the solution by ammonia and sodium hydroxide under ice-cooling, whereby a fraction of comparatively weaker, and another of strong, yellow bases were obtained. The latter fraction when dissolved in hot absolute alcohol yielded serpentine on slowly cooling the alcoholic solution as brilliant yellow, prismatic rods and plates melting at 153-54° (yield 4 g.; 0·08 per cent. on the wt. of the root). The mother-liquor yielded 1·5 g. (0·02 per cent.) of a reddish-yellow base, which could not be crystallised.

(ii) *Serpentinine*.—The fraction of the weaker yellow bases did not yield any crystal out of its solution in absolute alcohol even on long standing in the cold, but on addition of water to it till faint turbidity and slowly cooling in the ice-chest, serpentinine crystallised out in broad needles, which when filtered, washed with 60 per cent. alcohol and dried in air melted at 263-65° (decomp.) (yield 1 g.; 0·02 per cent. on the weight of the roots). The mother-liquor from serpentinine yielded a reddish-yellow amorphous powder on removal of the solvent, from which no further crystalline base could be isolated and which weighed 2·5 g. (0·05 per cent. on the roots).

Characterisation of the Alkaloids and their Salts.

Ajmaline, $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$.—It is white when amorphous and forms rectangular prismatic plates with a light tinge of amber on crystallisation out of moist ethyl acetate (Plate I). The crystalline base swells up at about 110° giving off its water of crystallisation, begins to soften at 150° and melts at 158-60°. It is easily soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate and chloroform, sparingly soluble in ether and benzene. In 1 p.c. chloroform solution it showed $[\alpha]_D^{33} = +128^\circ$. The air-dried crystals of ajmaline lost 15·1 p.c. on drying to constant weight over P_2O_5 in *vacuo* at 100°, which would signify 3 molecules of water of crystallisation. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2, 3H_2O$ requires H_2O , 14·2 p. c. [Found: (the dehydrated base) C, 73·0; H, 8·12; N, 8·8. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73·6; H, 8·0; N, 8·6 per cent.]. Though containing two nitrogen atoms ajmaline is a monoacid base and forms only one series of salts.

Ajmaline Hydrochloride.—The hydrochloride of ajmaline, when prepared by adding ethereal hydrochloric acid in an alcohol-ether solution of the base, is a white amorphous powder which melts at 253-55° without blackening. On dissolving it in hot water and slowly cooling the solution, it crystallises out with 2 molecules of

water in large, ambercoloured rhombohedral prisms or aggregates in very characteristic eight or multipetalled flowers, melting sharply at 133-34°. The air-dried crystals lost 9.1 p. c. water on drying to constant weight over P_2O_5 in *vacuo* at 100° and then melted at 253-55°. $C_{20}H_{26}N_2O_2 \cdot HCl, 2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 9.0 p. c. [Found: (dry hydrochloride) N, 7.3; Cl, 9.6. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 7.7; Cl, 9.8 per cent.). In 1 p. c. aqueous solution it showed $[\alpha]_D^{40} = +84.63^\circ$

Ajmaline chloroplatinate was obtained on addition of 10 p. c. platinum chloride to a concentrated solution of ajmaline hydrochloride under good cooling. It is easily soluble in alcohol, difficultly in water and melts at 217-18°. [Found: Pt, 17.9. $(C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 18.4 per cent.].

Ajmaline picrate, prepared by adding dry ethereal picric acid to an alcohol-ether solution of the base, formed a bright yellow semicrystalline powder, which was easily soluble in hot, difficultly in cold water and alcohol and crystallised out of the latter in rectangular plates melting at 126-27°. After drying to constant weight in *vacuo* at 100° the anhydrous picrate melted sharply at 223°.

The gold salt of ajmaline could not be obtained, as gold chloride is readily reduced by ajmaline as well as all the other bases of the two groups. Colour reactions of ajmaline and other bases are shown in Table I.

Ajmalinine, $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N$.—It crystallises in nearly colourless hexagonal prisms out of moist ethyl acetate (Plate II) melting at 180-81°, is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, sparingly soluble in ether and benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. $[\alpha]_D^{33} = -97^\circ$. It contains one molecule of water of crystallisation, the loss of weight being 4.6 p. c. $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N, 1H_2O$ requires H_2O , 5.0 p. c. [Found: (dehydrated base) C, 70.4; H, 7.1; N, 5.50 $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 70.4; H, 6.7; N, 4.1 per cent.).

Ajmalinine hydrochloride prepared by slowly adding dry ethereal hydrochloric acid to its alcohol-ether solution forms a white semicrystalline powder, which is soluble in alcohol as well as in water, shrinks at 213°, swells up at 235° and melts at 240-45° (decomp.). [Found: Cl, 9.1. $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 9.4 per cent.). $[\alpha]_D^{40} = -44^\circ$ (1 p. c. aqueous solution).

Ajmalinine chloroplatinate prepared in the same way as ajmaline chloroplatinate formed an amorphous powder. It is easily soluble

PLATE I.

Ajmaline
(from moist ethyl acetate).

PLATE II.

Ajmalinine
(from moist ethyl acetate).

PLATE III.

Ajmalicine
(from moist ethyl acetate).

PLATE IV.

Serpentine
(from 99.4 % alcohol).

in alcohol and water m.p. 254-58° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 18.1. $(C_{20}H_{23}O_4N \cdot HCl)_2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 17.9 per cent.].

Ajmalinine picrate prepared in the same manner as ajmaline picrate, formed a bright yellow powder, which is easily soluble in alcohol and difficultly in water, softens at 175° and melts at 200-5°.

Ajmalicine.—It crystallises out of alcohol and water in colourless silky needles and out of moist ethyl acetate in long prismatic plates (Plate III) melting at 250-52° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and chloroform, sparingly soluble in ether and benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether.

Ajmalicine Hydrochloride and Picrate.—Its hydrochloride and picrate, prepared as in the case of ajmalinine, formed white and bright yellow powders respectively. The *hydrochloride* was very sparingly soluble even in hot water, but easily in alcohol. It shrinks at 250° and melts at 260-63° (decomp.). The *picrate* is easily soluble in alcohol, difficultly soluble in water and melts at 212-15° (decomp.). Owing to the small quantity of the substance at our disposal the elementary analysis of the base and its salts could not be undertaken at present.

Serpentine, $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N$.—It crystallises out of 99.4 p. c. alcohol in bright yellow well defined prismatic plates (Plate IV) containing one molecule of water and melting at 153-54°. It is soluble in chloroform but is transformed by it on heating to a dark brown uncrystallisable powder melting at 245°. It is very sparingly soluble in alcohol when crystalline but easily so while amorphous, difficultly soluble in benzene and ether and insoluble in petroleum ether. It does not pass any light even in 0.5 p.c. chloroform solution, but its hydrochloride showed in 1 p.c. aqueous solution $[\alpha]_D^{40} = +188^\circ$.

The air-dried crystals when dried to constant weight in *vacuo* at 100 lost 7.0 p. c. of their weight. $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N + 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires H_2O , 7.1. [Found: (*Anhydrous salt*) C, 71.33; H, 6.3; N; 3.4. $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 71.4; H, 6.5; N, 4.0 per cent.).

Serpentine hydrochloride prepared by adding dry ethereal hydrochloric acid to a chloroform-ether solution of the base forms a cream coloured amorphous powder, which shrinks at 240° and melts at 260-61° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 9.13. $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 9.10 per cent.). The hydrated form separates from hot water as tufts of needles, m.p. 133-35°.

Serpentine chloroplatinate formed a pale yellow amorphous powder, which is soluble in alcohol and water, and crystallises out of

the latter in long needles, m.p. 217-20° under blackening. [Found: Pt., 17.9. $(C_{21}H_{23}O_4N \cdot HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 17.5 per cent.].

Serpentine picrate obtained by adding ethereal picric acid to a chloroform-ether solution of the base, formed a yellow amorphous powder, m.p. 261-62° (decomp.). It is easily soluble in warm alcohol, difficultly in cold alcohol and water.

Serpentinine.—It crystallises in brilliant yellow prismatic rods out of dilute alcohol, m.p. 263-65°. It is also easily soluble in ethyl acetate and chloroform, sparingly soluble in benzene and ether and insoluble in petroleum ether and water.

Serpentinine hydrochloride prepared by adding ethereal hydrochloric acid to the alcohol-ether solution of the base is a creamcoloured amorphous powder, and is soluble in alcohol and water m.p. 260-62°.

Serpentinine chloroplatinate is a yellow amorphous powder, soluble in alcohol, difficultly soluble in water, m.p. 260-263° (decomp.).

Serpentinine picrate prepared by adding ethereal hydrochloric acid to the alcohol-ether solution of the base, forms a bright yellow powder, which is easily soluble in alcohol but sparingly soluble in water, m.p. 225-27°.

The elementary analyses of serpentinine could not yet be undertaken owing to lack of a sufficient quantity of the substance.

II A. The Non-Alkaloidal Contents.

Examination of the Petroleum Ether Extract (A) Serposterin, C₃₀H₄₈O₂.—The petroleum ether soluble portion of the alcoholic extract of the roots was repeatedly shaken out with water in ethereal solution to completely remove any salts of the alkaloids, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent on the water-bath. The thick, dark green, liquid residue (25 g., 0.5 p.c. of the roots) was dissolved in 95 p.c. alcohol and kept for several days in the ice-chest. The light crystalline mass which separated out was carefully filtered in the cold, washed with cold alcohol and brought on a porous plate. The soft slightly greenish-white powder thereby obtained weighed 3 g. (0.6 p.c. of the roots); and melted at 125°. After repeated crystallisation out of the same medium, a snow white silky crystalline mass was obtained which melted sharply at 159-60°, the melting point remaining unchanged on subsequent crystallisations. It had $[\alpha]_D^{33} = -68.5^\circ$ (1.3 p.c. in chloroform). (Found: C, 81.82; H, 11.18. $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$ re-

quires C, 81·81 ; H, 10·9 per cent.). Mykosterin melts at 159·60° and shows $[\alpha]_D = -129\cdot2, -129\cdot5^\circ$.

Examination of the Waxy Matter.—20 G. of the waxy matter left after removal of the solvent from the mother-liquor of serposterin were saponified with alcoholic potash, the alcohol evaporated off and the residue extracted with ether, then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and again extracted with ether. On drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removing the solvent on the water-bath the first ethereal solution yielded about 8 g. of the acid portion (a), and the second ethereal solution 7 g. of a dark green non-acidic odorous liquid, (b).

Acid Fraction (a).—8 G. of this were converted into the barium salt in the usual manner to remove the non-acid impurities, the acid recovered from the salt and distilled under reduced pressure, whereby nearly all except about 2 g. of a dark brown residue distilled over at 190-94°/3·5 mm. as a nearly colourless liquid which congealed at about 20° to a white fatty mass. (Found: C, 77·3; H, 12·11. Oleic acid, $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$, distils at 285·5-286°/100 mm., congeals at 16° and requires C, 76·6; H, 12·1 p.c.; stearic acid distils at 291°/100 mm. melts at 69·6° and requires C, 76·0; H, 12·7 per cent.).

Saturated Acid.—The distilled acid was converted into the ammonium salt by passing ammonia into its ethereal solution and the ammonium salt dissolved in a very small quantity of absolute alcohol and kept in the ice-chest. The white crystalline ammonium salt, which separated out, was carefully filtered in the cold, washed with cold alcohol, and then extracted with a little ethereal hydrochloric acid. The acid obtained from the ethereal solution congealed at ordinary temperature and crystallised out of absolute alcohol, m. p. 58° (0·5 g.). Owing to lack of sufficient quantity further examination of the acid could not be undertaken.

Unsaturated Acid.—The mother-liquor from the ammonium salt of the above acid yielded about 2·5 g. of unsaturated acid, which congealed at about 15°, showed $n_D^{36} = 1\cdot4455$ and appeared to be chiefly oleic acid.

Reduction of Unsaturated Acid.—To 1 g. of the above liquid acid in absolute alcohol (2 c.c.) was added platinum black (1 g.) prepared according to the method of Wilstätter and Meyer (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1475, 2200), and the mixture was placed in a well-closed bottle

attached to a hydrogen generator and shaken in a shaking machine till absorption ceased. The resulting product was filtered from the platinum black and the filtrate cooled in the ice-chest. The white crystalline solid (about 1 g.) which separated out melted at 69° after recrystallisation out of absolute alcohol and showed no depression in its melting point when mixed with pure stearic acid.

Fraction (b), Alcohols.—The odorous, dark green, non-acidic liquid (b), (7 g.) was easily soluble in all the organic solvents and failed to give any crystalline product even on acetylation. Consequently it was subjected to distillation under reduced pressure when it yielded about 2 g. of a reddish-yellow liquid at $150-70^{\circ}/3$ mm. The product, thus obtained, took up bromine in chloroform solution at 0° . (Found: C, 79.9; H, 11.65. $C_{25}H_{44}O_2$ requires C, 79.8; H, 11.7 per cent.).

II (B). The Alkaline, Ether-insoluble Portion of Alcoholic Extract.

The Acid and Neutral Resins.—The alkaline residue left after ethereal extractions of the alcoholic extract of the roots was digested with hot water, which dissolved nearly all except about 4 g. of a reddish-brown resinous product, which was insoluble in acids as well as in alkalis, soluble in alcohol but insoluble in all other organic solvents. The filtrate from this neutral resin gave a dark brown slimy precipitate on acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid, which formed a chocolate coloured powder on drying (5 g.). The resinous acid thus obtained was soluble in alcohol but insoluble in all other organic solvents.

TABLE I

Colour Reactions of the Alkaloids of Rauwolfia Serpentina.

Reagent.	Ajmaline.	Ajmalinine.	Ajmalicine.	Serpentine.	Serpentinine.
Conc. H_2SO_4	Colourless	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow with greenish fluorescence	Light yellow
Conc. H_2SO_4 + $K_2Cr_2O_7$	Green	Dark brown	Dirty violet	Reddish brown	Greenish brown
Conc. H_2SO_4 + $KClO_3$	Bright yellow, then deep orange	Yellow, then dirty orange red	Deep yellow	Red	Bright yellow
Conc. H_2SO_4 + MnO_2	Violet fluorescence, then rose violet, finally orange red	Violet, then green, dirty green, finally dirty yellowish-green	Bluish-violet passing on to dirty green and finally dirty yellowish-green	Yellow, yellowish-green, and yellowish-brown	Dirty blue, then dirty greenish blue
Conc. HNO_3	Blood red	Yellow	Yellow	Deep yellow	Deep yellow
Fröhde's reagent	Light violet with a reddish tinge, then red	Light blue, then indigo, bluish-green, dirty green and finally grass green.	Yellowish-violet, then blue, dirty green, finally yellowish-green	Dirty yellowish-brown	Violet, then blue, greenish blue, finally dark green
Erdmann's reagent.	Rosy tinge developing into pink.	Greenish yellow, then dirty yellowish green.	Yellowish green, gradually passing on to brownish-yellow.	Light yellow, then straw coloured.	Light green then yellowish green.

TABLE II

Diagrammatic scheme of Analysis of Alcoholic Extract of Roots,

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